

THE YEMENI WAR AND SAUDI NATIONAL SECURITY

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Cite This Article: Saja Adel Ali, "The Yemeni War and Saudi National Security", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 9, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 46-55, 2024.

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Abstract:

The research deals with the Yemeni war and its impact on Saudi national security after 2011. During this period, the Arab region witnessed a wave of demonstrations and protests, which imposed a number of challenges on the national state at the local, regional and international levels. Yemen was among the countries affected by the waves of the Arab Spring, and the situation there developed until it reached the stage of war in 2014. Therefore, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia sought to provide justifications for its intervention and movement in Yemen. The vital importance of Yemen is summarized in the geostrategic location that Yemen oversees through its control over three bodies of water (the Arabian Sea - the Gulf of Aden - the Red Sea), in addition to the geographical proximity with the Kingdom. The Saudi political performance was represented by increasing military spending and expanding the network of economic relations, in addition to establishing security alliances to address imbalances and impose new balances other than the balances imposed by the Houthis after their coup against the outcomes of the National Dialogue Conference, through the Kingdom's resort to the military option. The Saudi perception came that the military option would contribute to securing the security of the Kingdom and preventing the surrounding threats that could affect the security of the Kingdom in the future. Its intervention came under the pretext of restoring legitimacy and fighting the Houthis, whom it considered rebels and coup plotters, in addition to helping the United States in its war on terrorism in order to gain international support. Therefore, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia relied in its political performance on an integrated economic and security strategy to enhance and expand regional and international cooperation on the economic and security levels, as security remains the primary goal of all countries and is the most important and most complex file for several reasons that differ from one country to another.

1. Introduction:

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia faces a regional climate that poses new challenges to its national security, including terrorist organizations, sectarian conflict and the struggle for power, in addition to doubts about Iranian intentions that emerged clearly with the events of the Arab Spring to expand and enhance influence in areas that are vital to the Kingdom. The Kingdom believes that it has priority in these areas over other countries because tampering with these areas is tampering with the areas of influence belonging to the Kingdom. Therefore, the Kingdom has followed a political performance characterized by seeking to enhance influence and dominance to confront counter-pressures issued by the United States, which saw the Arab Spring revolutions as an opportunity for change and enhancing freedoms and political openness, especially in the authoritarian regimes among them, and Iran, which saw the Arab Spring revolutions as an extension of the Iranian Islamic Revolution. Therefore, the security strategy of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia aimed to preserve the security of the Saudi regime in the face of military threats imposed by the Yemeni neighbor near the southern border, as well as ideological challenges coming across the national borders and posing a threat to the stability of the regime and the legitimacy of the ruling family on the internal political level. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia found the opportunity to play a regional role, especially after the change of the Iraqi political system after 2003, and Egypt's withdrawal from internal challenges. Consequently, the Kingdom will take more stringent and confrontational positions with Iran in order to achieve its goals and interests. The tension reached its peak against the backdrop of the accusations launched by the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia against Iran of launching a military attack against it. The Houthis began launching missiles targeting Saudi cities. In the heart of this competition, the two parties took irreconcilable positions that prevented any arrangement or formula for sharing influence in the region, which is the only way out in light of this competition for dominance and influence.

1.1. Value of the Study:

The importance of the study lies in identifying the nature of Saudi performance towards the Yemeni crisis and providing a comprehensive vision for it, in addition to knowing the capabilities that the Kingdom enjoys and the role it plays towards regional crises, as this period is a historical and decisive stage in the history of both countries. If the Kingdom succeeds, this will mean the birth of the new Yemeni state, and as for the Kingdom, this will lead to strengthening Saudi influence not only in the Gulf region, but as a regional competitor parallel to Iran and its influence in the region. Yemen gains its importance from its geostrategic location overlooking three bodies of water, in addition to its possession of the Bab al-Mandab Strait, which represents the gateway to global trade for the Gulf region. Therefore, any disturbances or changes in the balance of power in Yemen will be reflected in its direct effects not only on the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia but on the entire Gulf region.

1.2. Problem of the Study:

The outbreak of fighting on several different fronts, with the main players continuing to change their biases and affiliations, complicates the efforts made to reach a political settlement that leads to the stability of the situation in the Yemeni arena, through which the Saudi side can protect its national security from military attacks?

1.3. Hypothesis of the Study:

The thesis is based on the hypothesis that the Yemeni situation has an impact on Saudi national security, especially after 2011, and the development of those situations until the Houthis took control of the capital, Sana'a, which imposed new political and military balances, which were reflected in their direct effects on the security of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, which led to the

Kingdom resorting to the military option, as the security concern was the main motive behind the Kingdom's regional movement in Yemen.

1.4. Method of the Study:

The study employed several methods in order to present the facts in a simple and logical manner. The historical method was used in order to know the historical development of events, and the descriptive method through which the problem of the study and its dimensions will be described.

1.5. Procedure of the Study:

The study was divided into three sections distributed over a number of demands, in addition to the introduction and conclusion. The first section focused on the impact of the Yemeni war on the level of formulating national security goals and means at the internal and external levels. While the second section deals with the impact of the Yemeni war on the Saudi political interior and the competition and conflict within the ruling family. While the third section addressed the impact of the Yemeni war on the foreign security policies of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia by presenting a general vision of the Kingdom's foreign relations with major countries.

2. The Impact of the Yemeni War on the Level of Formulating National Security Goals and Means:

2.1. The Concept of Saudi National Security and its Challenges:

The Saudi vision of the concept of security was based on three factors: the strategic location of the Kingdom, the regional balance in the Arabian Gulf region, and the religious doctrine of the Saudi Basic Law (Ismail, 2014:68). The Saudi security concept in its early beginnings was based on securing a sufficient amount for the newly declared Saudi state. King Abdulaziz's desire was to consolidate the pillars of the Kingdom, control it, and know what was happening in its annexes (Abdel Baqi, 2015:25). Therefore, the Kingdom worked to obtain external support through many military and economic deals that the Kingdom concluded with foreign countries, most notably the United States of America (ibid:69). After consolidating the foundations of the Saudi state, the Kingdom focused its efforts on settling the Arab-Israeli conflict through peaceful means so that the region would not be exposed to more wars. The Kingdom considered Gulf security to be one of the main axes of Saudi national security. The Saudi role is essential in any security arrangements witnessed by the Arab region. During the sixties and seventies of the last century, the Kingdom focused its security efforts through a specific concept of security through which it sought to distance the Gulf region from the Cold War that existed between Moscow and Washington, in addition to the Kingdom's refusal to establish any American military bases in the region that would undertake the task of defending Waterways, and this rejection continued until the beginning of the eighties, as the Kingdom rejected in 1981 the project submitted by the State of Oman to the Gulf Cooperation Council, which stipulated giving Western countries specific tasks to defend the vital passages in the Gulf region, but this situation changed after the first Gulf War in 1980 and the second in 1991, as the Kingdom began to gather the Gulf countries around it to improve the level of coordination and security cooperation, and military cooperation, especially with the United States of America, received wide attention from the Council countries, based on the unity of purpose and destiny, in addition to geographical facts and common history (Al-Jazaery,2014:106). In 2000, the leaders of the Gulf Cooperation Council countries agreed to increase the strength of the Peninsula Shield Forces, as military cooperation achieved a qualitative leap through the signing of the GCC countries in the twenty-first session in the city of Manama on the Joint Defense Agreement for the Gulf Cooperation Council. This agreement defined many of the pillars of military cooperation, its foundations and priorities, and after 2000, the Kingdom found itself in the midst of a war against terrorism, which in turn led to the necessity for the Kingdom to seek to achieve stability by adopting policies to stop or prevent those attacks targeting in the first is the destabilization of Saudi national security. The Kingdom has faced a series of terrorist attacks targeting foreigners and residents of the Kingdom. The intensity of these acts has escalated and taken on other dimensions through the targeting of some oil facilities, which in turn represents a threat to the Kingdom's economy and an attempt to undermine its internal stability (Ismail,2014:105).The concept of security and defensive deterrence emerged in its clear form during the reign of King Salman bin Abdulaziz, especially after the recent appointments to security positions in the Kingdom, which demonstrated the pivotal role of security and defensive dimensions in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The appointment of Prince Mohammed bin Nayef as Minister of Interior and Crown Prince, in addition to the appointment of Prince Mohammed bin Salman, Crown Prince, as Minister of Defense, Advisor to the King, and Chairman of the Economic Council, all of this gives an indication that the direction of hard power will be dominant in the Kingdom's policy to confront the challenges and dangers surrounding it, and that Prince Mohammed bin Nayef will be the representative of the new National Security Strategy through his chairmanship of the Policy and Security Council (ibid:130). From here, the importance of the security factor appears on which the policy of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is based to defend the Kingdom's lands and achieve its security, and at the same time provide protection for the economic resources represented by the enormous oil wealth that coincides with the small population that is disproportionate to the vast area, which makes it an exposed target for regional and international powers. The Kingdom is not far from the dangers and threats surrounding it, which are numerous, the most prominent of which is Iran's attempts to control The region and the extension of its influence in it, after the successes it achieved in Iraq, Syria and Lebanon (Al-Shanbari,2016:63), the unrest that the Arab region has witnessed since 2011 has made clear the need for all the Gulf Cooperation Council countries in general and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in particular to strengthen the civilian aspect of the security challenges, as these challenges related to religion, ideology, economy and governance, these challenges are as important as the balance in military capabilities and the capabilities of the internal security forces, so the Kingdom tried to address this problem through a new program for government spending, after the regional developments and the complex strategic situations surrounding the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, especially with regard to the Iranian and Yemeni files, accompanied by files related to terrorist organizations, most notably what is known as Al-Qaeda and the Islamic State in Iraq and the Levant (ISIS), the files related to the opposition and political reforms, and at the time when the new Saudi leadership assumed power, it exploited the historical circumstance to carry out a package of reforms and reviews of its political performance and regional strategy through the arrangements of the Saudi ruling house from within and getting rid of the political and religious opposition in a way that achieves balance and harmony between the components of the political vision of the Saudi monarch, King Salman bin Abdulaziz, and his son, Prince Mohammed bin Salman, in order to stand up to the challenges and

threats facing the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, which exceed and exceed in their severity the traditional dimensions to extend to the ideological, cultural, political, social, and structural aspects at the internal level of the Kingdom (Al-Ghamdi,2018:59). Therefore, the decision of the Saudi monarch to reorganize the National Security Council came by establishing many mechanisms that guarantee flexibility in decision-making, especially those institutions responsible for shaping the political performance of the Kingdom. This announcement came within the framework of the Saudi leadership's efforts to improve the level of the security and political institutions of the Saudi state. This step comes within the context of the restructuring witnessed by the institutions of the Saudi state in response to the changes witnessed by the internal, regional, and international environment in a way that makes them capable of dealing effectively with the rapid transformations witnessed by the Arab region. In general, and the Gulf region in particular, at this stage, which will have consequences and implications for the future of the security and political stability of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as well as the strategic balances at the level of the Arab region (Abbas and Hashem,2016:9), and Saudi national security faces a group of threats at the internal and external levels, which are as follows:

2.1.1. Internal Threats to Saudi National Security:

- Political tensions resulting from the delay in political reform processes have posed a major challenge to the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as the Saudi citizen has become relatively outside the political process due to the personalization of the political decision-making process and its restriction to a specific group (Al-Kartani, 2016:13).
- The existence of conflict and competition between the traditional ruling elites in the Kingdom and other liberal and technocratic elites who aspire to participate in governance and benefit from the national wealth and privileges, as the political system in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is based on closed circles in the form of a follower and a followed (bin Sunaitan, 2004:157).
- The influx of large numbers of foreign workers coming to work in various specializations. On the other hand, the local experience in the Gulf countries is not sufficient in terms of numbers and experience to implement various vital projects to advance the economic development process. Therefore, this gap will be filled by bringing in millions of foreign workers (Bonayen, 2014:319). The number of foreigners in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia reached 459,624.4 million people according to the statistics of the Ministry of Finance and National Economy for the year 2014 AD, i.e. approximately 27% of the total population of the Kingdom, while this percentage rose to reach 40% in 2016 AD, especially in light of the modernization and reform process witnessed by the Kingdom in various fields, while the unemployment rate among Saudi youth rose at the end of 2017 AD to approximately 8.12% of the total population of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, while some believe that the real unemployment figures are much higher, especially among Saudi women, reaching approximately 35%, due to the private sector's preference for foreign workers over national workers (Mahboub,2019:164).
- Potential ethnic and sectarian conflicts: Although the majority of the population of Saudi Arabia are Sunni Muslims, this does not mean that there is a minority of Shiite Muslims living in the oil-rich eastern region. The danger lies in the possibility of the eastern region becoming independent and depriving the Kingdom of the enormous oil wealth that this region enjoys (Awda and Adly, 2015:175).
- The activity of the Salafi jihadist movement that has clearly emerged in Saudi Arabia since the bombings of residential complexes in the city of Riyadh on May 12, 2003, and the subsequent armed confrontations and violent bombings in various Saudi cities that have formed a clear feature of the contemporary period of Saudi history (Al-Shishani,2012:36).

2.1.2. External Threats to Saudi National Security:

- The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia fears the expansion of Iranian influence. This fear is imposed by Iran's geostrategic location, in addition to the growing Iranian role. The Kingdom views this role with suspicion and doubt. The reason for this is due to the ideological differences between the two countries, and at the same time due to the complex relationship between a regime that seeks to change the status quo, which is the Iranian regime, and another regime that seeks to defend and maintain the status quo, which is the Saudi regime (Al-Kartani, 2016:261). The third file relates to relations with the United States of America. Iran views the relationship between Riyadh and the American administration as being directed primarily against it. The fourth file relates to oil policies, whether those related to production quantities or prices. Iran interprets Saudi oil policies as tending to appease and meet Western desires by increasing production to reduce oil prices (Al-Sheikh, 2002:159).
- The issue of border disputes due to the lack of clarity in demarcating the borders between the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and some of the Gulf Arab states constitutes one of the most important obstacles to integration and instability that cannot be achieved in light of the continuation of these disputes (Awda, 2019:277).
- The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia fears the Iraqi oil economic project, as this will cause the Kingdom to lose its role as the largest oil producer on the regional level in the future. In addition, the political system in Iraq is a matter of doubt and concern, as any alliance or strategic integration between Iran and Iraq will make Iran a neighbor of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia on land, which poses a serious threat to various political, economic, social and cultural aspects (Al-Shishani, 2012:45).
- Despite the fact that the majority of Al-Qaeda's presence has moved to Yemen due to the security pressure it was subjected to while it was in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the Kingdom is still one of the main targets of the organization (Al-Hashemi, 2003:21).

2.2. Saudi National Security Objectives:

The national security objectives represent the basic pillar on which the Saudi national security strategy is based. National security today is linked to the foundations of the state's existence in its political sense, and includes defense, development, and economic welfare in its societal sense. These objectives that the state seeks to achieve are responded to according to the needs of the state's local environment and the external pressures imposed by the regional environment (Mabon, 2016:20). Accordingly, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia seeks to achieve a set of objectives, which are as follows:

First: Economic Objectives

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia seeks to confront the surrounding economic challenges represented by the instability of oil, the high population growth rate, as well as the increase in the rate of general military spending. Therefore, the Saudi government has taken a set of steps to diversify and increase. The 2030 vision aimed to grow the non-oil sector threefold by investing in other non-oil sectors such as renewable energy, mining, transportation, tourism, education, and other sectors, by supporting the employment of Saudi women and encouraging the private sector to employ more Saudi workers, in addition to increasing the rate of foreign investment. Therefore, economic experts described the 2030 vision as an ambitious vision in terms of the time frame and the size of the planned change (Al-Jaafari,2024), and the main elements of the 2030 vision include the following (Henderson,2024):

- Building an industrial sector and benefiting from renewable energy in the Kingdom.
- Improving water and electricity management.
- Supporting the private sector, whether as a percentage of the gross domestic product, or as a place for Saudis to find work.
- Developing the "Public Investment Fund".
- Developing cultural and entertainment projects.
- Starting to implement the "National Transformation Program" for the year 2020 AD. This program includes a set of goals represented in increasing non-oil revenues by three times, enhancing youth skills, and imposing an income tax on foreign workers.

Second: Political Objectives

The political objective of Saudi national security includes maintaining the stability of the existing regime, in order to avoid the transformations that occur in the structure of the ruling authority, by adopting a strategy that combines many methods and techniques, which leads to confirming the centrality of the ruling family and the power relations within it (Safran,1988:5). The competition witnessed by the Kingdom is a family competition that falls under the category of conflict and personal interest between the sons of King Abdulaziz themselves, especially between the sons of the Sudairi family and the rest of the non-brotherly princes. Therefore, we find that the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia witnessed a wide campaign of arrests coinciding with the announcement of King Salman bin Abdulaziz of Prince Mohammed bin Salman as Crown Prince, as the Kingdom witnessed attempts by some princes and tribal leaders to gain popular support by exploiting the state of anger resulting from the rise in fuel and electricity prices, the imposition of exorbitant taxes, and the depletion of economic resources as a result of the continuation of the Yemeni war. Therefore, these arrests were a means of getting rid of opponents or competitors who could pose a threat in the near future (online source,2 018). These opposition forces consist of three the main forces include liberals calling for political reform, radicals and religious forces opposing the political settlements that the Kingdom deals with the West and the United States of America in internal and external affairs. Therefore, the royal regime proposes solutions to these forces, which include suppressing opponents, in addition to allocating economic resources with the aim of calming tensions within the Kingdom, preserving the position of the ruling regime and weakening opponents (The Arab Spring Through Israeli Eyes, 2013:125).

Third: Security-Military Objectives

The security role of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia stems from two considerations, the first of which is related to the Saudi weight in the Gulf region, and the second is related to the importance of the Gulf for the security of the Kingdom in general. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia derives its importance at the regional level in the Gulf from several considerations, the most prominent of which is the Saudi coasts, which constitute 16% of the total Gulf coasts, making it the third Gulf state in terms of the length of its coasts after Iran and the United Arab Emirates. In addition, we find that the area of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia constitutes 49% of the total area of the Arab Gulf states (Ismail,2010:60), and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is the third largest Gulf state in terms of population, as the population of the Kingdom constitutes 11% of the total population of the Gulf after Iran and Iraq (ibid:266). In terms of military power, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is the second military power in the regional Gulf system, as the Kingdom has an army of 100,000 soldiers, in addition to more than 75,000 soldiers from the National Guard, which can reach more than 100,000 soldiers in the event of maximum mobilization in emergency situations. This army Equipped with the latest military equipment (Awda,2015:267). The Kingdom has moved towards reassuring the security aspect by working to increase military spending, as the Kingdom ranked fourth globally in 2014, after being ranked seventh in the previous year. This increase is due to internal and regional factors related to the state of unrest witnessed by the Arab region and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in 2011-2012. Internally, the need to increase the efficiency of the security services was linked to protecting the Saudi regime and the ruling family. Regionally, the Saudi-Iranian tensions regarding the situations in Iraq, Syria, Yemen, and Bahrain came, as the Kingdom adopted a major role in stabilizing the regime in some neighboring Gulf countries through direct military intervention to confront the protest movements in the Kingdom of Bahrain. The same can be said about the Saudi military intervention in Yemen, which led to more military spending on purchasing weapons during the years 2014, 2015, and 2016 (Abbas and Hashem,2016:5).

2.3. Saudi National Security Means:

These means combine multiple methods and tools that have been combined to achieve several goals at the same time. The goals that the state seeks to achieve are multiple, but they differ in terms of importance. Therefore, these means are chosen in a manner that is consistent with the importance that each goal occupies (Kngler, 2006:62). These means include the following:

First: Diplomatic Means

This stage of Saudi performance witnessed the leadership of new alliances through which the Kingdom was able to play a major role in the Arab region at a time when its role was limited to holding meetings and was satisfied with denunciation, condemnation, and non-interference in the internal affairs of countries. These diplomatic means ranged between good offices, mediation, negotiations, and other diplomatic means, in conjunction with setting reform paths for the affected countries (Mahboub, 2017:236). At the regional level, the Kingdom continues to support the Palestinian cause and considers it at the forefront of its concerns. It supports the right of the Palestinian people to self-determination and the establishment of their

independent state. As for Yemen, the Kingdom continues to affirm its position in support of the legitimate government in imposing its control over the land, in addition to the efforts made by the Kingdom to find a political solution in Yemen that ends the state of war and returns the Yemeni state to the Gulf Initiative and its implementation mechanism, and the results of the National Dialogue Conference to begin a new transitional phase to achieve stability, and then contribute to the reconstruction process (Al-Idrisi,2018:41). As for the international level, the Kingdom plays its role through the United Nations, Islamic organizations, and the Group of Twenty, as the Kingdom was able to hold three multilateral political summits, which are the summit The Saudi-American summit, through which the joint strategic vision between the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and the United States of America was announced, while the second summit included the Gulf Cooperation Council summit and the United States of America, where it was agreed to fight terrorism in all its forms and categories, while the third summit included the Arab-Islamic-American summit, which focused on the partnership between the Arab and Islamic countries and the United States of America to confront and combat extremism and terrorism, and witnessed the establishment of the first global center to confront extremist thought in the Saudi capital, Riyadh (Alaya,2018:40).

Second: Economic Means

The economic aid provided by the Kingdom is one of the means it uses to enhance its influence and position at the regional and international levels. The Kingdom focuses on its presence in its Arab regional environment and the Islamic world. The strength that the Kingdom enjoys enables it to use this aid as a tool for temptation and punishment in its political performance towards its surroundings. This aid may include strategic goals represented by diplomatic interests of a security and military nature, such as establishing military bases on the territory of the country receiving aid, and establishing a security alliance between the donor and recipient countries represented by joint military defense agreements and security cooperation in the field of combating terrorism, and ensuring votes in international organizations, in addition to supporting the political system of the recipient country (Alaya,2015:78). As for the economic level, the country receiving aid may be rich in various raw resources or a large consumer market for the products of the donor country's companies, or a labor force with low wages. Economic interests are determined and calculated according to different calculations. The country providing aid takes into account many criteria, including the percentage of the gross national product, when granting this aid. For the recipient country, as well as the level of trade exchange between the donor country and the recipient country (ibid: 79).

Third: Military Means

The Arab revolutions were the subject of controversy, tension and mutual accusation between Iran and other countries in the Gulf region, as Iran supported the protest movement in Bahrain while the Bahraini government and the GCC countries accused Iran of interfering in the internal affairs of the Kingdom of Bahrain. Tension prevailed between the Kingdom and Iran against the backdrop of the statements of Iranian Foreign Minister Ali Akbar Salehi, who said, "Saudi interference in Bahrain will have dire consequences" (Al-Wahili, 2016:78), accusing Riyadh of inciting sectarianism, and affirming that Iran is committed to not interfering in the affairs of other countries. The response of Saudi Foreign Minister Saud al-Faisal came, "It is unfortunate that we still hear such statements from Iran that serve only the purposes of inciting sedition, unrest and disturbances in the region" (ibid:79). On March 14, 2011, the Kingdom, with the support of a group of Arab countries, especially the GCC countries, sent thousands of soldiers as part of the so-called Peninsula Shield Forces across the bridge linking the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to the Kingdom of Bahrain. The officially announced mission of these forces was to help the Bahraini army restore order and protect the infrastructure. The basics of the country, and the Kingdom was able to achieve a political victory in the Battle of Bahrain, as this battle was fateful and strategic for the Kingdom, as the Kingdom considered this battle to be a battle with the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia itself and on more than one level, including securing the protection of the ruling family in Bahrain and the political system in it and preventing its transformation into a constitutional monarchy (Al-Kartani,2016:56). Based on the above, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia seeks to play an effective and influential regional role within the framework of the regional environment in which it exists, as the Kingdom, with its vast area, is the only country in the regional Gulf system that has border relations that link it to all the countries of the system (Al-Juhaishi, 2015:201).

Fourth: Media

Media is used by political actors to gain popular support in order to achieve their goals, as these media are used to shed light on certain purposes or specific issues among the political elite (Aelst and Walgrave, 2017:4). These media may give or withhold popular support from the decision-maker. In addition, the decision-maker views these media as a measure of the public's reaction to his policies and decisions, as political truth is built through these media. The public cannot control the facts presented to it, which contributes to reducing the danger and criticism that the political authority may be exposed to. The ruling family in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia owns television channels and media outlets that enjoy wide popularity, such as the Al Arabiya group of channels, the MBC group of channels, and the Asharq Al-Awsat newspaper, which puts it in constant contact with the Saudi public. In addition, these media outlets are characterized by continuous monitoring by the security authorities. At the same time, these media outlets constitute one of the biggest challenges facing the Saudi regime, especially when it comes to national issues and matters related to national security (Abdul-Baqi, 2014:44).

3. The Impact of the Yemeni War on the Saudi Political Interior:

3.1. The Succession and the Survival of the Ruling Family:

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is a religious political project that was founded on the alliance between the religious establishment and the political system. Governance in the Kingdom is a matter that is specific to the Al Saud family, and religion is a matter that is specific to the Wahhabi religious establishment. The Saudi state derives its legitimacy from its application of the provisions of Islam and its Sharia. There is no written constitution like other countries except for the Basic Law of Governance issued in 1992, which is an alternative to the constitution (2015:141). The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia shares with other Gulf countries its political system, which is the monarchy that is based on a single family in which rule is passed down hereditarily from father to son or brother. As a result of the spread of campaigns calling for the adoption of democracy, most of these countries have adopted a system of multiple institutions within the executive authority, such as the presence of a Council of Ministers, in addition to the legislative apparatus and the independence of the judiciary. Despite the absence of a written constitution in the

Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, it is governed according to the Basic Law issued by King Fahd bin Abdulaziz in 1992, which clarifies the basic principles of the three legislative, executive and judicial authorities, and the role and rights of the Saudi citizen. And his duties through the general framework of the Saudi system, in addition to including articles that define the religion of the state, the powers of the king, the Council of Ministers and the judiciary, and the Basic Law is considered the constitution that governs the Saudi state (Ismail,2010:46). The struggle over power is a common thing in the history of all ruling families in different countries of the world and in all historical periods, but that struggle and its intensity differs according to the influential circumstances and ruling figures, and despite the kinship between these figures, that did not prevent the struggle and competition to achieve their own interests (Al-Uthaymeen, 2018:44). The competition and conflict emerged in its clear form in conjunction with the developments and changes witnessed by the Arab region, and at the forefront of these reasons is the conservative thinking pattern that practices a policy that tends to keep the old on its feet and continue it until the end, because most of those holding power are elderly princes who oppose the new changes, which means severe instability in the Saudi system, so we find demands for reform and renewal, as the political system in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is beginning to die, its symbols disappearing one after the other, in addition to that, the transfer of power from fathers to sons means the continuation of the struggle over rule between the sons of the next generation of rulers and practicing that struggle and competition in the presence of the fathers and under their supervision, and although the senior princes relinquish power to their sons, they remain the first decision-makers in ministries and institutions, as they are By this concession they do not mean that they are about to give up the ministry or the institution, nor do they mean that they are about to give up their right to become kings. The prevailing philosophy here is based on transforming each ministry into a private institution that is sponsored by the prince and his sons, and through which he struggles with other princes other than himself to reach the throne of kingship or competes to seize more power. The issue is not a withdrawal or concession as much as it is an intrusion and strengthening of existence in front of other entities (Khayoun, 2015:142).

Although the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has intervened in Yemeni affairs since 1932, direct military intervention took place in 2015. This intervention was not new except in the form it took. This intervention coincided with King Salman bin Abdulaziz's announcement of the appointment of Prince Mohammed bin Salman as Crown Prince, bypassing the older generation of princes. Therefore, Prince Mohammed bin Salman found in the Yemeni situation an opportunity to prove his ability and get rid of the opposing princes. Prince Mohammed bin Salman saw the situation in Yemen as an ideal opportunity to ascend to the throne, relying on the great military capabilities of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in addition to the huge economic resources, as he assumed that the Saudi military forces would achieve a quick and broad victory against rebellious forces that lacked the necessary equipment to continue the war. Although the request of Yemeni President Hadi was not submitted to the Gulf Cooperation Council countries until 14 March 2015, the military preparation by the Kingdom was underway during the weeks that Yemeni President Hadi was in the city of Aden, through holding regular meetings with the Saudi ambassador to Yemen, Mohammed bin Saeed Al Jaber, and thus the choice was made to resort to military force in dealing with the Houthis (Lackner, 2019:54).

3.2. Prince Mohammed bin Salman's Political Reform Project:

3.2.1. The Emergence of Political Reform in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia:

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia witnessed two stages of reform, the first was in the early nineties of the twentieth century, and the second was in the early twenty-first century, and its pace accelerated after the events of September 11, 2003 (Al-Sharari,2015:216), the first stage of reform began in the nineties of the last century, in 1992 more than a hundred figures from scholars, preachers and university professors signed a petition to the late King Fahd called the Advice Memorandum, which contained ten points for political reform of the Saudi state at the internal and external levels. The memorandum spoke about the rights of scholars and preachers, the rights of minorities, reform of the judiciary, social facilities, and internal systems and regulations, and other points spoke about the administrative, financial, economic and military situation and the relationship of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia with the United States of America, and this memorandum was submitted to Ibn Baz and some Wahhabi sheikhs who endorsed this The memorandum and the amendments made to it were then submitted to King Fahd through Ibn Baz. The memorandum caused a great uproar within the ruling family and the popular and scientific circles, which saw the memorandum widely spread among them, which prompted the Al Saud to pressure the scholars and jurists who endorsed and supported this memorandum, most notably Ibn Baz and the Council of Senior Scholars, in order to take a position against the memorandum (Al-Wardani, 2007:111). The second phase of reform began after the events of September 11, 2003, when the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia began to implement a number of political reforms that aimed, in general, to strengthen the values of democracy and human rights, increase popular representation, and activate national dialogue between the various segments of the Saudi people (Jarghoun, 2016:288). American pressures were not the only motivation for reform, but were accompanied by internal pressures represented by the emergence of a peaceful reform movement that included a group of intellectuals, academics, and businessmen. In January 2003, a group of Saudi intellectuals, including one hundred intellectuals, submitted what was known as the Reform Statement to the Saudi Crown Prince, Prince Abdullah. This statement included demands for political, administrative, and economic reforms, the establishment of a constitution, the separation of powers, and judicial reform, in addition to establishing a Shura Council with broad powers. In April of the same year, 450 Saudi figures issued the Partners in the Nation document, which included demands examining the rights and conditions of the minority of Shiite Muslims in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, in addition to increasing their representation in various agencies and institutions. The political and religious state, then another document was put in place known as the Vision for the Present and Future of the Nation, which sought to alleviate the internal and external pressures that the Kingdom was exposed to by implementing a set of political reforms that included five basic axes, starting with the political axis that called for elections for the Shura Council and the independence of the judiciary, an economic axis that included the demand for the principle of justice in the distribution of wealth and economic planning, combating financial and administrative corruption and rationalizing public spending, a social axis that included the demand for human rights and guaranteeing women's rights and activating their public role, and the fourth axis related to civil society, while the fifth and final axis included an invitation from the Saudi government to hold a general national conference for dialogue and discussing the basic problems in the Kingdom (Saleh,2018:42).In light of the circumstances of this environment

calling for reform, a dialogue conference was held in the capital, Riyadh, in 2003 AD, called the Saudi National Dialogue. This conference was considered the first of its kind among various Islamic trends that included different categories of Saudi society (Al-Tayyar, 2005:208). This conference came as a necessary response to internal and external challenges. On the internal level, the source of threat and the weakening of national unity has become a cause of concern for the future of social peace in the Kingdom. On the external level, the new international equation represented by the United States of America's monopoly and its tendency to dominate the region makes it search for loopholes to infiltrate through in order to benefit from them in order to increase pressure towards the reforms it is drawing up (ibid:211). The reforms came to include organizing partial elections for municipal councils, and amending two articles of the Shura Council system, namely Article (17) and Article (23). According to the amendment to Article (17), the Shura Council has the right to express its opinion again on the proposals returned to it and then submit them to the King to take what he deems appropriate. As for the amendment to Article (23), it gave the Shura Council the right to propose and study the systems that He wanted it without obtaining prior permission from the King, and in April 2003, the Saudi government allowed the establishment of the National Society for Human Rights, and the year 2003 witnessed movements represented by allowing the establishment of the Saudi Journalists Association, and approving a non-governmental committee for human rights, in addition to the release of reformist detainees and human rights defenders (Al-Sharari,2015:262). These measures aimed to enhance peace and social stability, acknowledge intellectual and sectarian pluralism, confront exclusionary trends, expand popular participation at various levels, develop civil society institutions, and involve women in Saudi public affairs, in addition to a development in religious discourse with a social impact on new topics such as women, elections, human rights, minorities, and freedoms, especially freedom of expression, and not rejecting it completely as was prevalent before (Al-Shaib,2009:44). With the start of the Arab Spring events, reform projects reappeared from another, perhaps the most prominent of which was what was known as the statement Towards a State of Rights and Institutions, which constituted a qualitative shift in religious thought in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and this statement called for the separation of religion from politics, in addition to the use of concepts that were rejected by the religious movement until recently. Such as democracy, the principle of separation of powers, and the protection of civil liberties, which constituted a qualitative shift in enlightened religious understanding (Saleh, 2018:43). With the advent of King Salman bin Abdulaziz and his son, Prince Mohammed bin Salman, the role of religion diminished at the internal level of the Kingdom, and their era witnessed the stripping away of many of the powers of the Commission for the Promotion of Virtue and the Prevention of Vice, the arrest of many extremist religious preachers, and the establishment of the Entertainment Authority by Prince Mohammed bin Salman, which sponsors festivals and celebrations, and gave Saudi women the right to drive (ibid:44). In addition, these reforms were a means of changing some political figures who do not conform to the new directions of the Kingdom, such as the Commander of the National Guard, Minister of Economy, and Commander of the Naval Forces, Admiral Abdullah bin Sultan, and the former Crown Prince and Minister of Interior, Prince Mohammed bin Nayef (Illahi,2018:133). Prince Mohammed bin Salman, when he assumed the position of Minister of Defense, criticized the role of the former Crown Prince, Prince Mohammed bin Nayef, which included terrorist operations in the Kingdom, in addition to the incidents that affected pilgrims in the city of Mecca in 2016. The Yemeni war contributed to concentrating and expanding the political influence of the Al Saud family, especially after the Saudi leadership took a number of decisions that included the dismissal and appointment of a number of figures. The fields of internal security, defense, and foreign policy became limited to the ruling family and individuals close to it. The former spokesman for the military coalition in Yemen, Major General Ahmed Al-Asiri, was promoted to Deputy Chief of Intelligence, and the Commander of the Joint Special Operations in Yemen, Major General in Yemen, was promoted. Major General Fahd bin Turki bin Abdulaziz to the Commander of the Saudi Land Forces (Seiler, 2024).

4. The Impact of the Yemeni War on the Foreign Security Policies of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia:

4.1. The Impact of the Yemeni War on the Saudi-Iranian Competition:

Iran was able to pressure the Kingdom and put it in a state of continuous security anxiety, which was witnessed in the third Saada war when military confrontations broke out between the Houthis and the Saudi army on the southern border of the Kingdom with Yemen, which enabled Iran to infiltrate spies into the Kingdom through Yemeni passports and recruit Houthis to carry out this mission, in addition to the possibility of Houthi elements infiltrating other countries neighboring Yemen such as the Sultanate of Oman, which allows them to form intelligence and military cells or form pressure elements on the Gulf governments at a later time by disrupting Gulf security and stability, and redirecting the armed southern movement logistically from the southern regions of the Kingdom through the soft belly of the Yemeni-Saudi-Emirati-Omani geographical borders from the desert surroundings through what is called the Al-Badi' Triangle, as the sands of Yemen meet the three countries and it is not unlikely that this desert will turn into military and intelligence bases filled with terrorist organizations and close to the borders of the Kingdom, which allows them to threaten the security and stability of the Kingdom at any moment, on the other hand, if the southern movement's demands for secession succeed, the northern Yemeni Houthis will demand independence and secession, similar to southern Yemen, and thus a state will be established next to the Kingdom with a different religious ideological nature that owes its loyalty to Iran, which is something that the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia does not want close to it (Hamid, 2018:211). After 2014, Yemen turned into an arena for regional conflict and competition between the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and Iran. The Iranian policy based on supporting its ideological allies and strengthening their influence led to increasing Saudi fears that Iran would establish a Shiite crescent loyal to it in these areas. The Kingdom fears that the growth of Iranian influence in Yemen may lead to the ignition of rebellion in the eastern and southern provinces of the Kingdom, so the Kingdom relied on financing successive Yemeni governments to ensure its internal security (Abdullah, 2018:250). The Kingdom considers that tampering with Yemen's security is tampering with its national security, which is an integral part of Arab national security. Iranian practices are not merely political and economic ambitions that every country has the right to pursue through legitimate means, but rather expansionist ambitions at the expense of others. The Houthi movement in northern Yemen and the armed southern movement in southern Yemen, which is supported by Iran, are among the means used by Iran to implement its goals and ambitions in the region and to encircle the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Therefore, the security of the Kingdom and the security of Yemen cannot be separated, as Yemen represents the natural extension of the Arabian Peninsula, and whatever the political differences, based on

Arab brotherhood, common interest, and the same destiny, this will ultimately be imposed on the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as Yemen, along with the Gulf Cooperation Council countries, constitute a single strategic bloc (Hamid, 2018:213).

4.2. The Impact of the Yemeni War and the Repercussions of the Gulf Crisis and Qatar's Withdrawal from the Coalition:

The Qatari leadership followed a political performance characterized by extreme pragmatism towards the Arab protests and uprisings, as its movements were primarily in accordance with Qatari interests. Qatar saw that the Arab revolutions were an opportunity that it could exploit to consolidate its regional position at a time when the rest of the other Gulf states remained silent at the beginning of the protests. Then the Gulf states, led by the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, later paid attention to the Gulf region after the outbreak of those protests in both the Kingdom of Bahrain and the State of Yemen due to their importance to the Gulf national security, which gave Qatar an opportunity to practice a policy of extending influence in countries outside the Gulf region. It was one of the countries most involved in overthrowing the former Libyan regime and one of the first to participate in supporting the Saudi opposition and provided support to the Muslim Brotherhood in Egypt during the first parliamentary elections following the revolution of December 25/January, but the other Gulf states, led by the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, began to exert pressure on Qatar to abandon its policy (Muhammad,2015:123), and the Gulf crisis began as a result of the withdrawal of ambassadors from the capital, Doha, in March/ In March 2014, Riyadh, Manama, and Abu Dhabi announced their decision to withdraw their ambassadors from Doha after the escalation of the dispute between them and Doha due to their opposition to the Egyptian events at the time, especially with regard to the overthrow of President Mohamed Morsi, who belonged to the Muslim Brotherhood. The estrangement and tension continued until November of the same year until the success of Kuwaiti mediation that restored normal relations between Qatar and the Kingdom, followed by improving relations with other countries, the Emirates, Bahrain, and the return of the ambassadors of the three countries to the capital, Doha. However, the crisis of 2017 brought the dispute back to the forefront for new goals and reasons, as the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the Emirates, Egypt, Bahrain, and Yemen announced on June 5, 2017, the severing of diplomatic relations with Doha. Then events accelerated, and the group took the decision of a political, economic, and commercial blockade. Qatari flights were banned, land and sea borders were closed, and Qataris in some of the boycotting Gulf countries were deported. What was known as the Arab Spring revolutions formed a source of conflict. Qatari-Emirati: Qatar opposed the removal of President Mohamed Morsi and rejected the Emirati moves on the Yemeni coast, which constituted a turning point in the relations between the two countries. As for Qatari-Saudi relations, despite the agreement to remove Yemeni President Ali Abdullah Saleh and support the Syrian opposition against the regime to limit Iranian influence, the disagreement came, according to what was published by the Saudi Press Agency, that Qatar supports terrorist and sectarian groups in Syria, Libya, and Yemen. Although Doha participated in Operation Decisive Storm, it issued a statement stating that it respects the sovereignty of other countries and does not interfere in their internal affairs, so it announced its withdrawal from the coalition. As for Egypt, the Egyptian Ministry of Foreign Affairs announced that the decision to cut relations came because of Doha's defense of President Morsi and support for terrorist organizations, headed by the Brotherhood, and harboring its leaders against whom judicial rulings were issued, in addition to promoting the ideology of Al-Qaeda and ISIS, and insisting on interfering in Egyptian affairs (Hamada, 2018:77).

4.3. The Impact of the Yemeni War and Building Regional and International Alliances with the United States of America:

The relationship between the United States of America and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is not a relationship of equality or parallelism between a strong ally with multiple interests and goals that it seeks to achieve in a specific region, and an ally that needs support, protection, and the provision of advanced combat systems and weapons, with both allies knowing that each party needs the other for security, defense, and economic reasons. Both parties also know that despite the differences and differences that have emerged in recent years, they cannot do without the other, and that the options before them in this regard are limited. With the start of the Arab Spring revolutions, the United States of America began to view the Arab Spring revolutions in the Middle East as the beginning of a new opportunity through which this region can be reshaped in order for this region to remain fragmented and in the service of American interests, meaning that the United States of America remains the only important power in the world and not the dominant one because it will be dominant through these countries that it has placed under its control. Thus, the United States of America will tend to choose places that serve its interests and strategy, and thus it will replace the United States of America adopted a high-cost hegemonic power strategy after the Cold War (Al-Barsan, 2015:32), and the United States of America seeks to calm tensions, not resolve them, and prevent any power from growing or forming an alliance against its interests and goals. Therefore, American positions were characterized by hesitation towards some revolutions, especially the Yemeni one, which contributed to the emergence of disagreement and differences of opinion with the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, as the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, which is waging a war with Iran on Yemeni territory, fears that Iran will abandon its nuclear weapons ambitions in exchange for Western concessions, which may lead to Iran being given a free hand in the region to be the implementing ally that helps the United States of America achieve its goals and strategy in Afghanistan, Iraq, the Gulf, Syria, Lebanon and Yemen, which is something that the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and Washington's allies in the Middle East cannot accept under the current circumstances, as the Yemeni crisis has increased the disagreement between the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and the United States of America, especially after the Houthi coup against the legitimate government and the deterioration of the security situation in Yemen. The United States of America keeps the Houthi card to confront Al-Qaeda in Yemen. What increased the Saudi concern and skepticism about the US position and its view of the Houthis is that the US administration did not pay attention to the threat posed by the Ansar Allah movement to the security and stability of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and the Gulf Cooperation Council countries, and the Iranian threat posed by Iran, which controls four Arab capitals, which means Iran's control over the Arabian Gulf, the Strait of Hormuz, the Bab al-Mandab Strait, the Red Sea, and all the way to the Mediterranean Sea (Mahboub,2015:8).

5. Conclusion:

According to the above, the Saudi move towards regional crises was based on two internal and external considerations: the first is related to its awareness of the potential risks to the internal situation of the Kingdom, and the second is related to the influence and status of the Kingdom at the regional level, which requires the Kingdom to be a key player in light of the new balances witnessed by the Arab region. In conjunction with the outbreak of the Arab Spring revolutions, the Kingdom of Saudi

Arabia witnessed a shift in its political performance represented by an increase in military spending and the practice of effective diplomacy to establish regional and security alliances to confront Iranian influence. The Kingdom seeks to play an effective regional role within the framework of the environment in which it exists, so the Kingdom has worked for decades to establish a close partnership with the Sana'a government. The Kingdom considers Yemen an internal affair in which the repercussions of the turbulent situation have imposed military intervention more than once. Yemen constitutes a direct source of threat because the control of the Houthis will lead to an increase in Iranian influence in the Arab region and the Gulf in particular, and close to the southern borders of the Kingdom. Therefore, the Kingdom worked to diversify its sources of strength. On the internal level, it began to arrange and organize political decision-making institutions. And on the security level, on the external level, this was represented by the network of economic relations, providing aid, and establishing security alliances to confront Iranian influence.

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